

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF DENOISING METHODS FOR BRAIN FLAIR MRI IMAGES: GAUSSIAN, MEDIAN, NLM, BM3D AND HYBRID APPROACH

Kambarov Bakhriddin Panji ugli¹, Khurramov Ruslan Erkin ugli², Makhamatdinov Abdul-Aziz Karamatdinovich³

¹PhD student at the Tashkent State University of Economics, gambarov.b.p1997@gmail.com,

²Lecturer at the Department of Information Technologies and Exact Sciences, Termez University of Economics and Service, ruslanxurramov852@gmail.com,

³PhD student at the Tashkent State University of Economics.

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***Annotatsiya.** Ushbu maqolada bosh miya FLAIR MRT tasvirlarini shovqindan tozalashning 4 ta klassik usuli - Gaussian filtri, Median filtri, NLM (Non-Local Means), BM3D va gibrid (Gauss+Median) yondashuvi - qiyosiy tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqot real FLAIR T2 MRT tasviri (512×512, DICOM format) asosida olib borildi. Sifat baholashda PSNR va SSIM metrikalari qo'llanildi. Olingan natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, NLM usuli PSNR=45.30 dB va SSIM=0.9735 ko'rsatkichlari bilan barcha usullardan, shu jumladan gibrid kombinatsiyalardan ham ustun keldi. Gibrid Median+NLM usuli PSNR=37.19 dB natija berdi. Tadqiqot natijalari FLAIR MRT rasmlarini shovqindan tozalashda NLM usulidan foydalanish samarali ekanligini tasdiqlaydi.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** MRI denoising, FLAIR MRI, Gaussian filter, Median filter, Non-Local Means, BM3D, PSNR, SSIM*

***Аннотация.** В данной работе представлен сравнительный анализ четырёх классических методов шумоподавления - фильтра Гаусса, медианного фильтра, метода нелокальных средних (NLM) и алгоритма BM3D - а также гибридного подхода (Gaussian + Median), применяемых к FLAIR-изображениям МРТ головного мозга. Исследование проводилось на реальном FLAIR T2 МРТ-снимке (512×512 пикселей, формат DICOM). Для объективной оценки качества шумоподавления использовались метрики пикового отношения сигнал/шум (PSNR) и индекса структурного сходства (SSIM). Экспериментальные результаты показывают, что метод NLM продемонстрировал наилучшие показатели: PSNR = 45,30 дБ и SSIM = 0,9735, превзойдя все остальные методы, включая гибридные комбинации. Гибридный подход Median + NLM показал PSNR = 37,19 дБ. Полученные результаты подтверждают, что метод нелокальных средних является наиболее эффективным алгоритмом шумоподавления для МРТ-изображений головного мозга и рекомендуется для применения в клинической визуализации и конвейерах предварительной обработки данных.*

***Ключевые слова:** шумоподавление МРТ, FLAIR МРТ, фильтр Гаусса, медианный фильтр, метод нелокальных средних, BM3D, PSNR, SSIM*

***Abstract.** This paper presents a comparative analysis of four classical denoising methods - Gaussian filter, Median filter, Non-Local Means (NLM), BM3D, and a hybrid (Gaussian+Median) approach - applied to brain FLAIR MRI images. The study was conducted on a real FLAIR T2 MRI scan (512×512, DICOM format). Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) metrics were used to evaluate denoising quality. Experimental results demonstrate that NLM achieved the highest performance with PSNR=45.30*

dB and SSIM=0.9735, outperforming all methods including hybrid combinations. The hybrid Median+NLM approach yielded PSNR=37.19 dB. The findings confirm that NLM is the most effective method for denoising brain FLAIR MRI images and is recommended for clinical imaging preprocessing pipelines.

Keywords: MRI denoising, FLAIR MRI, Gaussian filter, Median filter, Non-Local Means, BM3D, PSNR, SSIM

Introduction: Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is a widely used non-invasive imaging technique that provides detailed structural information and functional characteristics of internal organs [1]. Deep analysis of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) data plays a crucial role in clinical decision-making processes, particularly in the planning of surgical procedures. However, the presence of noise in MRI images leads to a degradation of image quality, which adversely affects image processing and analysis stages, including segmentation, classification, and visualization. As a result, the level of diagnostic accuracy decreases, and the risk of incorrect conclusions increases. Therefore, in order to ensure effective subsequent image processing and achieve reliable results, it is essential to reduce or eliminate noise in MRI images at the initial stage [2]. Noise is present in almost all types of image data; however, its sources and characteristics vary depending on the imaging modality and acquisition process. In medical imaging, particularly MRI, common noise sources include thermal noise, Gaussian noise, and scanner-related noise [3]. Gaussian noise is another type of noise which is additive and independent. The noisy image is as expressed in

$$In_{i,j} = I_{i,j} + n(i,j) \quad (1)$$

where In is the noisy image, I is the original image and n defines the additive noise [4].

Various classical denoising methods have been widely applied to reduce noise and improve image quality. Although these approaches demonstrate a certain level of effectiveness in noise removal, their performance on real brain FLAIR MRI images has not been sufficiently investigated through systematic evaluation using quantitative metrics. This study aims to address this gap by comparatively analyzing the performance of several classical denoising methods on a real FLAIR T2 MRI image. The results are evaluated using quantitative metrics such as PSNR and SSIM.

Methodology: Noise reduction in MRI Images has been an important field of research for years and this has led to the creation of different denoising methods. These methods can be categorized into traditional filtering approaches, patch-based statistical methods, model-driven frameworks like BM3D, and newer deep learning techniques [5]. The Gaussian filter is a popular smoothing filter used to reduce noise and blur in images. It operates by convolving the image with a Gaussian kernel, which is a two-dimensional Gaussian distribution [6]. Equation (2) shows the Gaussian filter formula

$$G(x,y) = 1/(2\pi\sigma^2) \cdot \exp(-(x^2 + y^2)/2\sigma^2) \quad (2)$$

where σ is the standard deviation of the distribution, assuming the distribution has a mean of zero at $x = 0$. The distribution is shown in image - 1.

image-1

Median filtering is widely used for eliminating impulse (salt-and-pepper) noise by replacing each pixel value with the median of its neighboring pixels. This non-linear approach preserves edges more effectively than Gaussian filtering. However, when applied to continuous-tone images such as MRI, it may distort fine textures and suppress low-contrast features, potentially affecting diagnostic accuracy [7]. Equation (3) presents the median filter formulation:

$$I'(x, y) = \text{median}\{I(i, j) \mid (i, j) \in \mathcal{N}(x, y)\} \quad (3)$$

where $I'(x, y)$ is the filtered image, $I(i, j)$ represents the intensity values of pixels within the neighborhood $\mathcal{N}(x, y)$, and the median operator selects the middle value after sorting the intensities within the window.

image-2

The Non-Local Means (NLM) algorithm estimates each pixel value as a weighted average of all pixels in the image, where the weights are determined by the similarity between local neighborhoods (patches), enabling effective noise reduction while preserving fine structures [8]. Given a discrete noisy image $v = \{v(i) \mid i \in I\}$, (4) the estimated value at pixel i , denoted as $NL[v](i)$, is computed as a weighted average of all pixels in the image:

$$NL[v](i) = \sum_{j \in I} w(i, j) v(j), \quad (5)$$

where $w(i, j)$ are the weighting coefficients that depend on the similarity between pixels i and j . These weights satisfy the following conditions:

$$0 \leq w(i, j) \leq 1, \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{j \in I} w(i, j) = 1. \quad (7)$$

The weights are typically defined as:

$$w(i, j) = \frac{1}{Z(i)} \exp \left(0 - \frac{\|v(N_i) - v(N_j)\|^2}{h^2} \right), \quad (8)$$

where

$v(N_i)$ and $v(N_j)$ denote the intensity vectors of square neighborhoods (patches) centered at pixels i and j ,

h is the filtering parameter controlling the degree of smoothing,

$Z(i)$ is a normalization constant given by:

$$Z(i) = \sum_{j \in I} \exp \left(0 - \frac{\|v(N_i) - v(N_j)\|^2}{h^2} \right). \quad (9)$$

Here, N_k represents a square neighborhood of fixed size centered at pixel k .

image-3

The Block-Matching and 3D filtering (BM3D) algorithm is one of the most advanced and widely used image denoising techniques, known for its high efficiency in suppressing noise while preserving fine structural details and textures. The core idea of BM3D is to group similar image patches into 3D stacks and perform collaborative filtering in the transform domain. This approach exploits the non-local self-similarity property of images, enabling effective separation of signal and noise components. The BM3D algorithm operates in two main stages: a basic estimation stage based on hard-thresholding and a final estimation stage based on Wiener filtering. Both stages involve a 3D transform and its inverse applied to grouped similar patches [9]. The overall BM3D framework can be expressed as:

$$\hat{X} = \mathcal{J}_{3D}^{-1}(\Phi(\mathcal{J}_{3D}(Y))) \quad (10)$$

where Y denotes the noisy image, \mathcal{J}_{3D} and \mathcal{J}_{3D}^{-1} represent the forward and inverse 3D transforms, respectively, and $\Phi(\cdot)$ denotes the shrinkage operator applied in the transform domain.

Stage 1: Hard-Thresholding (Basic Estimate)

$$\hat{X}^{basic} = \mathcal{T}_{3D}^{-1}(\gamma(\mathcal{T}_{3D}(Y))) \quad (11)$$

In this stage, a coarse estimate of the clean image is obtained by applying hard-thresholding $\gamma(\cdot)$ to the transform-domain coefficients, effectively removing noise-dominated components.

Stage 2: Wiener Filtering (Final Estimate)

$$\hat{X} = T_{3D}^{-1}(W \cdot T_{3D}(Y)) \quad (12)$$

where the Wiener weights are defined as:

$$W = \frac{|T_{3D}(\hat{X}^{basic})|^2}{|T_{3D}(\hat{X}^{basic})|^2 + \sigma^2} \quad (13)$$

Here, \hat{X}^{basic} is the basic estimate obtained from the first stage, and σ^2 represents the noise variance. The Wiener filtering stage refines the denoised result by adaptively weighting the transform coefficients based on the estimated signal-to-noise ratio.

image 4

The two-stage structure of BM3D, combining hard-thresholding and Wiener filtering in the transform domain, enables superior denoising performance by effectively balancing noise suppression and detail preservation.

In addition to the classical denoising methods, a sequential hybrid Median+NLM approach was also evaluated in this study. This hybrid strategy was designed to first suppress local impulse-like noise using median filtering and then refine the image using the NLM algorithm. However, the experimental results showed that this combination did not outperform the standalone NLM method. This may be explained by the fact that the median filtering stage tends to suppress fine textures and low-contrast structures, which reduces the effectiveness of the subsequent NLM stage that relies on neighborhood similarity for detail preservation (image 5).

image – 5

To objectively assess the denoising performance, quantitative evaluation metrics including Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) were employed. PSNR reflects the fidelity of pixel intensity reconstruction, whereas SSIM assesses the preservation of structural and perceptual information in the image.

Mean Squared Error (MSE) is a simple metric that calculates the average squared difference between the pixel values of two images.

MSE is defined as:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (I_1 - I_2)^2 \quad (14)$$

where I_1 and I_2 represent the pixel values of the two images, and n denotes the total number of pixels.

A lower MSE value indicates better image quality. The term “better image quality” refers to how clearly and accurately an image represents the original object or scene, including the level of detail and visual fidelity [10].

Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) is a widely used metric for evaluating the quality of reconstructed images. It is defined by comparing the maximum possible signal value of the original (ground truth) image with the error introduced by the reconstruction algorithm.

Mathematically, PSNR is expressed as:

$$PSNR = 20 \cdot \log_{10}(MAX_I) - 10 \cdot \log_{10}(MSE) \quad (15)$$

where MAX_I denotes the maximum possible intensity value among the red, green, and blue components in an RGB image. In the case of 8-bit images, this value is equal to 255.

The term MSE represents the Mean Squared Error between the reconstructed high-resolution (HR) image and the ground truth image in terms of pixel intensity values.

PSNR is measured in decibels (dB), and higher PSNR values indicate better image quality [10].

The Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) evaluates the similarity between two images or videos — the original and the reconstructed image. SSIM is defined as:

$$SSIM(x, y) = [l(x, y)]^\alpha \cdot [c(x, y)]^\beta \cdot [s(x, y)]^\gamma \quad (16)$$

where x and y represent the two images being compared, and higher SSIM values indicate better image quality.

In this formulation, different components are used to compare the images:

- l denotes luminance and compares the overall brightness of the images;
- c represents contrast and measures the difference between the brightest and darkest regions;
- s refers to structure and evaluates the similarity of local intensity patterns.

Additionally, the equation includes three positive constants α , β , and γ .

SSIM is considered more suitable than PSNR for evaluating the perceptual quality of super-resolution (SR) algorithms, as it correlates better with human visual perception. However, SSIM is computationally more complex than PSNR, as it requires the calculation of local statistics [10].

Results and discussion: In this research, four conventional denoising techniques (Gaussian, Median, NLM, BM3D) along with one hybrid approach (Median+NLM) were employed to remove noise from images. The experiments were performed on a single real FLAIR T2 MRI

image, and the results were assessed using PSNR and SSIM evaluation metrics. The numerical results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Quantitative comparison of denoising methods on FLAIR T2 MRI image

Method	PSNR (dB)	SSIM
NLM	45.30	0.9735
Median	37.25	0.9251
Hybrid M+NLM	37.19	0.9224
Gaussian	36.16	0.9226
BM3D	34.16	0.8400

As can be seen from the table, the Non-Local Means (NLM) algorithm outperformed all other methods, achieving the highest performance metrics. The method attained PSNR = 45.30 dB and SSIM = 0.9735 values, indicating that it successfully reduced noise while maintaining high fidelity of structural details in the image. This superior performance is attributed to the NLM algorithm's capability to exploit similarities across distant regions of the image.

The Median filter also yielded relatively satisfactory results, validating its efficiency in attenuating impulse-type noise. Nevertheless, owing to the partial smoothing of fine textures, it produced inferior performance metrics compared to NLM.

The hybrid Median+NLM approach, unexpectedly, failed to achieve superior results. Conversely, it exhibited performance degradation relative to the standalone NLM method. This can be attributed to the loss of fine and critical structural features during the median filtering stage, which subsequently diminished the efficacy of the NLM algorithm.

The Gaussian filter exhibited moderate performance, reducing noise through image smoothing; however, this process inadvertently blurred important structural details.

The BM3D algorithm showed the poorest performance among all tested methods. This result may be attributed to non-optimal parameter configuration or its sensitivity to the noise characteristics inherent in real MRI acquisitions.

Experimental results demonstrate that NLM achieved the highest PSNR of 45.30 dB and SSIM of 0.9735 on the FLAIR T2 MRI image, outperforming all classical and hybrid filtering approaches. Hybrid combinations did not improve upon standalone NLM performance, suggesting that NLM alone is sufficient for effective denoising of FLAIR MRI images.

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